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ENLIGHT RISE- RESEARCH AND INNOVATION AGENDA WITH AND FOR SOCIETY: LEVERAGING DIGITAL INNOVATION FOR A GREENER AND HEALTHIER EUROPE

WP No	Del. Rel. No	Del No	Title	Lead beneficiary
1	D1.3	D3	Three large strategic project proposals submitted (e.g. MSCA-COFUND)	UT

Nature	Dissemination Level	Related to Del. No (if applicable)
Websites, patents filling, etc.	Public	

Description (short)
Co-led by UBx and RUG, this deliverable provides an overview of the various research oriented proposals that have been submitted by the ENLIGHT alliance over the course of the ENLIGHT RISE project.

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Introduction and context

ENLIGHT is a European University formed by ten comprehensive research-intensive universities from ten European countries¹ (University of the Basque Country in Spain, University of Bern in Switzerland, University of Bordeaux in France, Comenius University Bratislava in Slovakia, University of Galway in Ireland, Ghent University in Belgium, University of Göttingen in Germany, University of Groningen in the Netherlands, University of Tartu in Estonia, Uppsala University in Sweden).

ENLIGHT has obtained funding from the European Commission in the framework of the Horizon 2020 Science with and for Society (SwafS) work programme. The ENLIGHT RISE project (Research and Innovation agenda with and for Society) seeks to strengthen the research and innovation dimension of the ENLIGHT alliance.

One of the key goals of the ENLIGHT RISE project is to encourage and enable collaborative projects among partners within the alliance. Our aim for the project was to submit 3 large strategic project proposals for ENLIGHT. While at the proposal stage we stipulated that a strategic proposal should include 2 or more ENLIGHT partners, it was later decided that such a proposal should include at least 3 ENLIGHT partners to avoid "accidental" collaboration. At the same time, partners agreed that a strategic proposal should fall under one of the five ENLIGHT challenge domains. Various funding schemes were to be considered, such as, but not limited to, Horizon pillar II, MSCA actions such as Cofund and Doctoral Networks, COST etc.

Thanks to the ENLIGHT RISE initiatives such as the R&I Support Group and the five pilot focus groups (see deliverables 11, 12, and 16) the development of tools such as the ENLIGHT R&I Observatory (see deliverable 10) and partner search functionalities, as well as distribution of the mobility awards (see deliverables 13-15), we have seen a significant number of project submissions over the course of ENLIGHT RISE. Additionally, some partner universities have allocated their own resources to help build ENLIGHT collaborations. As of the time of finalizing this report (August 28th, 2024), we have surpassed our original goal by more than five times, with 17 strategic proposals submitted; six of these have been funded. Overall, 23 proposals involving at least two ENLIGHT partners have been submitted, with eight projects securing funding. The recent matchmaking event held on April 29th, 2024, along with the last mobility awards,

¹ ENLIGHT has expanded to formally include the University of Bern with the start of ENLIGHT 2.0 in November 2023. Therefore, below we have included UBern in the count of involved ENLIGHT partners per submitted proposal from that date onwards, even though UBern has not been a formal partner in ENLIGHT RISE (but has been included in some of the ENLIGHT RISE working groups).

are expected to yield further positive outcomes even after the conclusion of the project period.

Strategic proposals submitted

As mentioned above, to be considered strategic a proposal must gather at least three partners from the alliance. According to this definition, over the course of the project a total of 17 project proposals have been submitted. Out of these, at the time of this report, 6 projects have successfully secured funding, while another one has progressed past the first stage of the call. 9 proposals have been rejected, and 1 is currently awaiting final evaluation. The following table provides an overview of the project submissions involving at least 3 ENLIGHT partners up to August 28th.

ENLIGHT flagship area	Coordinator	ENLIGHT Partners	# of ENLIGHT partners	Call	Outcome
Health and well-being	VU Amsterdam	RUG, UU, UPV/EHU	3	HORIZON-MSCA-2021-DN-01	Granted, Acronym: Biocatcodeexpander
	UGent	UU, GAL	3	AMAI call (local Belgian call)	Rejected
	UGent	RUG, UU	3	HORIZON-MSCA-2023-PF-01: MSCA Postdoctoral Fellowships 2023	Rejected
	GAL	UGent, INRAE (UBx), UBern	4	NutriBrain – ERA4Health 2024	Rejected
	UBx	RUG, CU	3	HORIZON-HLTH-2024-ENVHLTH-02	Selected for Stage 2, Acronym: AIRYOUTH
Equity	UGOE	UT, UU, UGent, UBx	5	HORIZON-CL2-2022-DEMOCRACY-01	Rejected
	UGent	RUG, UT	3	HORIZON-CL2-2021-TRANSFORMATIONS-01	Granted, Acronym: ReConnect China
	GAL	UBx, UU	3	HORIZON-CL2-2024-DEMOCRACY-01-01	Rejected
	GAL	UBx, UU, UGOE, UT	5	HORIZON-CL2-2024-DEMOCRACY-01-04	Rejected
	GAL	UBx, UU, UGOE	4	HORIZON-CL2-2024-DEMOCRACY-01-05	Granted, Acronym: EMMELO

	GAL	UGent, RUG, UT, UU	5	Strategic Research Development Scheme, College of Arts, Social Sciences and Celtic Studies, University of Galway	Granted, Acronym: UNITY
Culture and creativity	UBx	UPV/EHU, UT	3	HORIZON-CL2-2024-HERITAGE-01-05	Rejected
Digital revolution and Impact of digitization	OpenAIRE	UGent, UU, UGOE	3	HORIZON-INFRA-2021-EOSC	Rejected
	UBx	UGent, UGOE, UT (+ RUG associated partner)	5	HORIZON-MSCA-2023-DN-01-01	Rejected
	Goeteborgs Universitet	UU, UGOE, UBern	3	HORIZON-INFRA-2024-TECH-01	Submitted
	UGent/ RUG	CU, UT, UPV/EHU, UGOE	6	HORIZON-CL2-2024-DEMOCRACY-01-08	Granted, Acronym: DELIAH
Climate Change	UGent	UBx, GAL	3	HORIZON-CL6-2024-CLIMATE-01-5	Granted, Acronym: WOODSTOCK

Overall submitted proposals

The table below summarizes the overall project submissions per various calls with at least two ENLIGHT partners involved. In total, 23 projects have been submitted, 8 have been granted, 1 is selected for stage two, 10 have been rejected and 4 are still awaiting evaluation.²

ENLIGHT Flagship area	# of submitted projects with ENLIGHT partners as coordinators and/or participants	Call under which the proposal was submitted	Outcome
Equity	4	HORIZON-CL2-2024-DEMOCRACY	2 rejected; 2 granted (project acronyms: EMMELO, DELIAH)

² A complete list of all submitted proposals with acronyms/titles will be provided in the final report due to confidentiality reasons.

	1	HORIZON-CL2-2022-DEMOCRACY	Rejected
	1	HORIZON-CL2-2021-TRANSFORMATIONS	Granted (project acronym: ReConnect China)
	1	Research Foundation - Flanders	Granted (project title: Experienced social segregation in daily activity spaces)
	1	Strategic Research Development Scheme, College of Arts, Social Sciences and Celtic Studies, University of Galway	Granted (project acronym: UNITY)
Health & Well being	1	NutriBrain – ERA4Health 2024	Rejected
	1	Health Research Charities Ireland (HRCI Funding scheme)	Submitted
	1	HORIZON-HLTH-2024-ENVHLTH-02	Selected for stage 2 (proposal acronym: AIRYOUTH)
	1	AMAI call (local Belgian call)	Rejected
	1	HORIZON-MSCA-2023-PF-01: MSCA Postdoctoral Fellowships 2023	Rejected
	1	HORIZON-HLTH-2024-STAYHLTH-01-two-stage	Rejected
	1	HORIZON-HLTH-2024-DISEASE-03-08-two-stage	Submitted
	1	HORIZON-MSCA-2021-DN-01	Granted (project acronym: Biocatcodeexpander)
	1	HORIZON-EIC-2024-PATHFINDEROPEN-01	Submitted

Digital revolution and Impact of digitalization	1	HORIZON-INFRA-2021-EOSC	Rejected
	1	HORIZON-MSCA-2023-DN-01-01	Rejected
	1	PUT-call Estonian Research Council, call PR1990	Granted (project title: Living segregated lives: Exploring changes in spatial inequalities in digitally transforming societies)
	1	HORIZON-INFRA-2024-TECH-01-01	Submitted
Culture and creativity	1	HORIZON-CL2-2024-HERITAGE-01-05	Rejected
Climate change	1	HORIZON-CL6-2024-CLIMATE-01-05	Granted (project acronym: WOODSTOCK)

Success stories

This section highlights two ENLIGHT project proposals listed in the previous tables that illustrate how ENLIGHT initiatives have proven pivotal in facilitating partner searches and enhancing proposal submissions. Drawing from the project coordinators' and the support teams' inputs, the two following sections outline, in a narrative manner, how partners have been brought together to form their consortia.

AIRYOUTH project

AIRYOUTH is a project proposal led by the University of Bordeaux, which involves the University of Groningen and Comenius University, that passed the first stage of the call HORIZON-HLTH-2024-ENVHLTH-02-06-two-stage "The role of environmental pollution in non-communicable diseases: air, noise and light and hazardous waste pollution."

The coordinator of the AIRYOUTH project has shared the story of how they formed their consortium. They began by initiating contact with the UBx Europe Office in May 2023 to discuss the project call. By June 6, UBx researchers held their first meeting, and by June 30, they started sending out partner requests through the ENLIGHT network.

A "partner search" was sent to European counterparts of ENLIGHT universities after the project coordinator's team had identified the expertise required using the R&I expertise tool of the Enlight R&I Observatory. On the day of the request, Comenius University responded eagerly, followed by the University of Groningen on July 17th. These ENLIGHT universities also brought clinical expertise from the university hospitals of each city (Slovak Medical University SZU and University Medical Center of Groningen UMCG) into the consortium.

The coordinator credits the good collaboration with the UBx ENLIGHT R&I Support Group team and the ENLIGHT tools such as the R&I Observatory, and also the Focus Group Health and Well-being, for facilitating partner identification. These tools enabled UBx to pinpoint required expertise and approach suitable partners strategically.

By September 1st, 2023, the first version of the AIRYOUTH project was ready, and subsequently submitted in the first stage of the call by September 19th. Commenting on the challenge of finding partners, the coordinator emphasized difficulties finding scientific expertise that the coordinating team did not have in their network and ensuring these expertise areas were present in partners eligible for Horizon Europe. By joining the consortium, ENLIGHT partners provided the required scientific expertise.

EMMELO project

A researcher from the University of Galway successfully submitted a project under HORIZON-CL2-2024-DEMOCRACY-01-04 call. The project involves a consortium of 4 ENLIGHT partners – in addition to the University of Galway, it includes the University of Bordeaux, Uppsala University and the University of Gottingen as well as 4 other partners not from the alliance.

"The first thoughts about the possible proposal submission emerged in October 2022 when I started the BRRIDGE project (10.3030/101079219)," recalled the coordinator. "In January 2023, I became active in the ENLIGHT RISE Focus Group on Equity and mobilized it to attempt to find further partners through the ENLIGHT network" and "to ask for additional expertise and encourage interested researchers to get in touch with me." Through this effort, it was possible to connect with two researchers from Göttingen. By May 2023, another networking opportunity arose. "When I heard about University of Galway's ENLIGHT Research networks 2023 calls, I used this opportunity to get additional resources". Once received, the funding from the University of Galway helped to build an ENLIGHT network (DEMOGLOBE), proving useful to start looking up ENLIGHT partner universities for complementary missing expertise. Thanks to this network, it was possible to identify a researcher from Uppsala and one from Bordeaux.

“The fact that DEMOGLOBE enabled me to hire Research Assistant who helped with networking, follow-ups, and writing was invaluable.”

Conclusions and way forward

Thanks to multiple ENLIGHT RISE initiatives, as well as the availability of funding by some partners for ENLIGHT collaborations, we have seen a significant number of joint submissions by ENLIGHT partners. Although with the ending of ENLIGHT RISE there will no longer be dedicated funding for research collaboration within the alliance, we believe we can continue this positive trend. This can be done via initiatives within the new Erasmus ENLIGHT 2023-2027 project such as ENLIGHT Thematic Networks, EU Strategic Watch, Europe Support Network, and continuous exchange of partner searchers between the members of the ENLIGHT RISE R&I Support Group beyond the ENLIGHT RISE project end date, as well as via the links and research networks created via the pilot focus groups (see deliverable D16).